

DON'T DISK-ARD THE PAST: PRESERVING FLOPPY DISK KNOWLEDGE FOR THE FUTURE

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Abstract – The knowledge surrounding floppy disk technology spans institutional, community and generational domains. However, much of this expertise risks being lost due to insufficient documentation and generational shifts. This paper presents the initial steps of the *Future Nostalgia* project, which aims to identify, preserve, and make accessible the diverse body of knowledge related to floppy disks. By bridging institutional expertise, active community contributions, and intergenerational knowledge, this initiative seeks to ensure the longevity of both the material and intellectual heritage associated with floppy disk technology.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Floppy disks, once a ubiquitous data storage medium, have now become largely obsolete and difficult to access. Whilst physical disks are still found in collections across memory institutions, the knowledge necessary to interpret, maintain, and retrieve data from them is scattered across a variety of domains. These include specialized knowledge held within institutions that have worked with obsolete storage media, niche communities such as retro gaming enthusiasts, and individuals with hands-on experience using floppy disks and their hardware.

However, many experts with this knowledge are either retiring or passing away, putting the information at risk of being lost. With the first patents for floppy disk drives dating back to the early 1970s [1], it is crucial to document and centralize this expertise to ensure it remains accessible for the future.

Some systems, such as popular retro computers like the Amiga and Commodore, are well-documented, and there is a wealth of support for both the disks and their associated hardware and file systems [2], [3]. However, less common systems present a unique set of challenges. Memory institutions may hold floppy disks from these obscure computers, machines that were mainly used within research or business settings, such as WANG, Lexitron and International Computers Limited (ICL) disks. These are difficult to preserve and access due to limited information on the specific hardware and software involved. In these cases, while capturing flux streams [4] may be possible, creating usable disk images or enabling original software emulation remains a challenge—or is simply unfeasible.

Additionally, the preservation of these disks is hindered by the challenge of obtaining the proper hardware to read them. Devices like Amstrad disk drives or 8-inch disk systems are not only difficult to set up but also often lack sufficient documentation on how to do so. The obscure formats of these disks make it difficult to even create backups, let alone

maintain or clean the equipment needed to work with them.

Even when a disk image can be acquired, the process of accessing and reading the files from it presents further obstacles. Emulators are not always designed to extract all the necessary data, as seen with issues surrounding Amstrad disks [5], and operating systems—especially those used by older machines—can be difficult to navigate.

This paper outlines a guide to capturing the specialized knowledge surrounding floppy disks to address the many challenges faced by the digital preservation community.

II. SOURCES OF KNOWLEDGE

To compile a comprehensive guide, we are gathering knowledge from multiple sources, each offering a distinct perspective and expertise. These sources include institutional knowledge, community contributions, and generational expertise.

1. Institutional Knowledge

Memory institutions and archival organizations may have large numbers of floppy disks within their collections. However, technical expertise and access to the necessary hardware and tools vary widely across institutions. Furthermore, documentation on how to handle, recover and preserve data from floppy disks is often inconsistent and varies per institution.

To address this gap, the project team conducted two expert workshops, bringing together professionals actively working with, or with previous experience of preserving floppy disks. Participants were recruited through direct invitations and an open call to the wider community to gather expressions of interest and joined us from different time zones across the world. These sessions have helped shape the scope and outline of the guide and the topics to be covered. Discussion also focused on the audience of the guide and the knowledge and understanding of the topic that can be assumed. It was noted that in creating this guide there was no desire to re-invent the wheel, and participants were encouraged to share existing resources that should be referenced and signposted from the guide.

After these workshops a draft guide will be created and shared with workshop participants and the wider community, inviting feedback and contributions.

2. Community Contributions

Online communities, such as retro computing and gaming enthusiasts, continue to engage with floppy disk technology, often developing innovative solutions for hardware and software compatibility. These communities create advancements such as modern floppy controllers, but their documentation and dissemination of knowledge remains informal, ad hoc and dispersed. Additionally, their primary focus is often on emulation and accessibility rather than long-term preservation.

To incorporate insights from these communities, we are sharing materials with key groups, including volunteers at the Centre for Computing History [6] centre and members of the GreaseWeazle user forums. GreaseWeazle is one of the primary floppy controllers used in the field, and discussions within its community provide valuable technical insights [7].

3. Generational Expertise

Many individuals who worked with floppy disks during their heyday hold invaluable expertise that has not been formally documented. This knowledge is at risk of being lost as generational shifts occur. Janneke van Dalen's *Share That Knowledge* guide [8] highlights the importance of intergenerational knowledge transfer and provides strategies for preserving expertise.

A key challenge is that much of this knowledge resides in people's memories, and they may not recognise its value until asked. Extracting and recording this information requires targeted interviews and collaborative efforts to document insights that might otherwise be lost. This will be done on a pilot basis and will focus on four key areas:

Developing tools that bridge the gap between floppy disk hardware and modern computers - This includes floppy controllers like GreaseWeazle, as well as tools that enable floppy drives to interface with modern computers, such as the FluxEngine [9].

Cleaning floppy disks for imaging - Many floppy disks have been stored for long periods of time in inappropriate conditions and are deteriorating. This issue has been highlighted by a number of different talks and blogs [10], [11], [12]. Exploring and experimenting with techniques for cleaning these disks is another important aspect of this project.

Cleaning and maintaining floppy disk hardware and computers - With the discontinuation of manufacturing for many floppy disk drives, maintaining and servicing these aging pieces of hardware is critical. Sharing knowledge on proper care and repair techniques is essential for long-term preservation.

Working with emulators and other tools to extract files - Emulators are used to extract files and render them in their original context. This process also involves creating disk images from flux streams and managing these images to ensure accurate preservation.

III. DEVELOPING A GUIDE FOR KNOWLEDGE PRESERVATION

This guide builds upon the discussions and engagement from the *iPRES 2024* workshop on obsolete floppy disk technology [13]. The workshop revealed a strong demand for further development of this work and highlighted the need for a dynamic guide that allows ongoing contributions.

The guide also draws upon lessons learned from similar efforts, such as the *Archivist's Guide to Kryoflux* [14]. The creators of this guide have provided helpful insights into potential pitfalls and best practices, which have influenced the structure and approach of our initiative.

To ensure broad participation and accessibility, the guide incorporates multiple avenues for contribution:

- Expert workshops and interviews with practitioners in the field
- Outreach to experts who worked with floppy disks during their peak usage
- Open submission pathways for community members outside the traditional digital preservation field
- Distribution through various platforms, including subreddits, GitHub, Facebook

groups, and Mastodon, to engage a diverse audience

An important aspect of this guide is its support from the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) who are exploring new publication avenues. This approach facilitates external contributions and ensures the guide remains as current as possible. Given the rapid evolution of floppy disk tools and techniques, a lengthy review process would be impractical.

IV. CONCLUSION

The *Future Nostalgia* [15] project is currently creating a guide that will be an evolving resource, and contributions are welcome. While this initiative has made significant progress, there are still gaps to address. For instance, hardware distribution remains uneven across the community, and more knowledge needs to be captured.

Additionally, this project presents an opportunity to reflect on the challenges and successes of this collaborative approach to knowledge preservation. Future iterations will incorporate lessons learned and refine methods for engaging and documenting expertise. Ultimately, this guide seeks to bridge institutional, community, and generational knowledge to safeguard the legacy of floppy disk technology for future generations.

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